

Pesticides residues in Indonesian environment: our responsibility

Edhi Martono

*Department of Plant Protection, Faculty of Agriculture
University of GadjahMada, Yogyakarta, Indonesia*

Pesticides were and still are used throughout Indonesian agriculture. From farmers to agricultural decision makers, all still believe that pesticides can not be separated from agriculture. With the existence of tropical disease insect vectors, pesticides are also very popular armory in public health. Although the intensive use of pesticides dated back only in the 1950s, its impact had been recognized since late 1970s, a mere twenty years after. Yet up to today, despite the implementation of eco-friendly yield increase rice planting movement such as the National Integrated Pest Management Program on rice, the use of pesticides among farmers are still high and the number of registered pesticides are in the level of two – three thousands trade names (Untung 2004; Direktorat Pupuk & Pestisida 2012).

Quantitatively, the use of pesticides in Indonesia can be anyone's guess. The real number is very hard to find, and then if you have any figures, whether it seem ensuring or threatening will depend on who or which agency give you the data. Official sources varied on their data presentations, and it is hard for anyone, including scientists, to decide which data and information really telling the truth, if not downward confusing. The official data that came from the Directorate of Fertilizer and Pesticides, under the Directorate of Infrastructure, Ministry of Agriculture in 2014 show that there were 315 active ingredients which were registered to the National Pesticides Committee by 394 companies. In total there were 3005 trade names registered. The most number of trade names on a single active ingredient registered was found on a herbicide, with no less than 265 different names (Direktorat Pupuk & Pestisida, 2014).

The massive use of pesticides in this country leave traces of residues almost in and on any places where they are used. Agricultural fields and plantation sites will be the ones that we can expect to encounter the existence of abundant residual pesticides, in many molecular structures, which may or may not be harmful. But we should also aware of the fact that in residences, in buildings, houses and homes, the residues are present, as aerosols formulations are still very popular for most people under the threat of malaria, dengue hemorrhagic fever, elephantiasis and several other vector-borne diseases. They are also used to de-insectize places, as all the year round in tropical area like ours the insects often become nuisances. In lesser degree, pesticides are also used in other places such as dairies and fisheries enterprises, sporting arenas, parks and

road shadebushes or roadside trees. Dairies and fisheries use pesticides to control animal diseases and fish parasites and predators, while sport arenas mostly use pesticides for aesthetics and pest controls. With parks and roads, the purposes of using pesticides must be routine maintenance, especially when there were weeds, pests or diseases which disturb the bushes and the trees.

Regardless of the causes, the use of pesticides need to be arranged carefully, not only before and during the application, but also after the work had been done. Here the term residues become key word. Pesticides residues, as defined by Matsumura (1975) are pesticides which are left after an application and did not kill or directly react with their targets, but they still retain some of its toxicity and may be harmful to the environment and everything on and in it. There is time dimension as one deciding factor in considering the importance of pesticides residues. Although each and every pesticides will leave residues in the environment, their quantity and quality over time will vary greatly. Many earlier pesticides, which were became likable as they were believed to be the end of many disturbing organisms, were broad spectrum in their target. Also, some were designed to last as long as possible so that they would kill more targets. The term "residual spray" was very popular and most pesticides were applied with the presumption that they would last until the targets were all decimated.

The persistence of the first commonly used pesticides, i.e. organochlorine or chlorinated hydrocarbon, are very notorious. They stayed in the environment, both on non-living and living entities. These organochlorine pesticides last long, because they are not easily broken down into less poisonous compounds, and many are lipophilic and hydrophobic. That means they will stay in the fat tissues of living organisms. With the euphoria of having what was thought as panacea to pests problems at that time, other aspects such any adverse effects toward everything surrounding the sites of application were not considered. Afterward, Carson (1962) popularly showed that pesticides use became precursor of some living organisms disappearances, as the process of bioaccumulation and biomagnification of harmful compounds in pesticides residues resulted in the decline of some important predatory species, even some resulted in their extinction.

Carson writings had a very pronounced impact on the way people manage the environment, especially after it was known that we are under the threats of synthetic chemicals which not only come from pesticides. They also come from other chemicals used daily as necessities for our more modern and convenient living as well. USA then established the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) to regulate and control any matters dealing with the environment, pesticides included. US Department of Agriculture (USDA) although a little bit late, also start to limit pesticides use. Studies about the

negative effects of pesticides increased, and many blame the indiscriminate use of these chemicals as the cause of several environmental disasters, such as the extinction of non-target species, the onset of hard-to-cure or even incurable diseases, and the heavy damages to non-living environments. In the end of 1960s and early 1970s, several organochlorine pesticides such as DDT, Endrin, Dieldrin and Aldrin were banned to be used in agriculture in many developed countries, although as vector control chemicals they still used in some, mostly underdeveloped, countries. But other non-organochlorine pesticides such as organophosphorous, carbamates and plant-inspired synthetic pyrethroids continued to compete, filling the demands as pesticides had become some kinds of obligatory input in farming and other activities.

Pesticides residue analysis also started to gain its importance, as both qualitative and quantitative data and information will provide the basis for pesticides residual knowledge on given temporal and/or spatial dimensions. This knowledge is used to determine whether any pesticides would be fastly degraded into their less harmful derivatives, what kind and how much residue present in any substances (especially food and feed), how long they will stay on living organisms' body, what harmful effect they will incur, and many other information necessary to construct and establish regulations and policies on pesticides. Other information must also be considered, since ceding these policies has to be done comprehensively and holistically. Therefore the data on pesticides residual is not the only one to rely on. It has to be collaborated with other facts and information on pesticides demand and supply, pests weeds and diseases as agricultural problem as well as vector related diseases as public health problems in the community, preference of the community in using pesticides, synthetic chemical usage habit of the community and so on.

The qualitative and quantitative demand of describing the existence of pesticides residue gave rise to not only the hardwares and the methods to handle them, but to the environmental safety concept such as MDL (Maximum Dosage Limit), MRL (Maximum Residual Limit), ADI (Acceptable Daily Intake), NOEL (No Observable Effect Limit) and several others terms and definitions pertaining to environmental toxicology. While experts in this field may continue to grow each year, many countries still lacking in non-specialists who are able to evaluate, combine and collate many aspects of pesticides use in the country. This aside from the fact that pesticide residue analysis is very costly. Pinchus et al. (1999) showed that out of almost 5.5 million Baht for external costs of chemical pesticide use in Thailand, 5.1 million Baht or 92% were used for analyzing residues in food, and that was only in fruits and vegetables. Although the development of the analysis techniques become more and more sophisticated, with almost the tiniest amount of trace molecules can be detected, the budget to

perform those analysis is the real constraint for many underdeveloped countries. While technically and scientifically speaking we are capable of doing many methods according to the newest protocol such as QuEChERS (those which are “**Q**uick, **E**asy, **C**heap, **E**ffective, **R**ugged and **S**afe”) with a lot of practical instrumentations (advertisements of Waters Corp, 2018, for instance), however, on its financial part it is still unclear about who will be responsible.

This may be the reason why in Indonesia pesticides residual analysis are mostly done either as academic research or as clarifications on products that were suspected of being contaminated with pesticides metabolites and residues. What were found mostly were organochlorine from a long ago application when they were still permitted and abundantly used in agricultural and public health sectors, and as can predicted, these compounds lodged inside animals but almost could not be found in plant products. Sudaryanto et al. (2007) and Rahmawati et al. (2013) both analyzed the level of several organochlorine in fishes, especially on *Clarias* sp. (catfish) in West Java by the latter, but they found the levels were still below the MRLs. Organochlorine residue of Alpha-endosulfan was also observed on tea (Setyarini et al, 2014) but again the level was not significant at all. The QuEChERS method of analyzing organochlorine pesticides (18 kinds) on lettuce was confirmed to be excellent by Boes et al. (2015), but what they did was justified the methods, not in search of certain quantity of any organochlorine pesticides. It should be realized the the common use of organochlorine mostly had happened more than forty years ago. But to be on fair side, it also means that technical-wise, no problem and difficulty was encountered in applying the newest methods for these compounds.

On the other hand, although their use until presently are still on high levels, researchers on the residues organophosphates, carbamates, synthetic pyrethroids, glyphosates up to the more recent such as neonicotinoids found them in low concentration (Alen et al., 2016; Hasibuan, 2016). However, complaints from receiving countries of several fruits, vegetables and estates' products (palm-oil, tobacco, tea) often happen on our export commodities (Harmoko et al., 2015; Hasibuan, 2016). The seriousness of this accusation was enhanced by the fact that many of Indonesian export commodities do not undergo quality control particularly on their pesticides residues content before they were sent to the buyers.

From the government side, people often confuse the Pesticide Committee task—a multi-departmental agency issuing permits to distribute and trade pesticides in this country—with inspecting and safeguarding the use, application and management of pesticides. These tasks is actually the realm of other different committee, i.e. the Fertilizer and Pesticides Inspection Committee

(KP3, *Komisi Pengawasan Pupuk dan Pestisida*). The Pesticides Committee works on the registration of pesticides which will be traded, distributed and used in Indonesia. Although one of its technical job description is to ensure that pesticides must have short persistence and should not be harmful to the community and the environment, when the pesticides had already been in use, what happen to them must adhere to the policies, rules and regulations of the FPIC. One of the task of the FPIC is to promote safe and responsible use of pesticides, including monitoring residual levels of any pesticides used in Indonesia.

From the short writing above, we can see these facts about the state of pesticides residues in Indonesia: The pesticides residues can be found in many parts of ecosystem in Indonesia, living and non-living, as pesticides use are still high and happen in many sectors, not only in agriculture and public health. The presence of residues mostly known after there were complaints or rejection of Indonesia products by exporting countries based on the pesticides residues analysis that those countries performed. Indonesia is capable of doing the pesticides residues analysis, but most of the analysis done were for academic purposes, or clarifications of any lodged complaints. There is no clear rule and regulation on who will be responsible for any financial budget that should be incurred while the costs for pesticides residues analysis is high.

The tasks of monitoring, inspecting and safeguarding pesticides use in this country must be more descriptive, informative and clearly defined by the agency which was established for this purpose. The awareness on the adverse effects of pesticides should be more intensively and continuously promoted so that problem of pesticides residues can be minimized.

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